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SYNERGY OF SUSTAINABLE DESIGN AND CULTURAL HERITAGE

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ABSTRACT

Development of the built environment ought to proceed without loss of the local character of each individual place; I assert that architecture, although “globalized” in many ways, should follow the principles of *Inter-local* sustainable design, which, while being multicultural, retains and enriches local identity. Education should focus to a universal consideration of the links between ecology, available means and way of life, traditional heritage and technological development in the search of inventive bioclimatic applications.

The synergy of related approaches, under a continuous broadening of the cognitive base of education and simultaneous development of new topology and shape optimization techniques, will lead to innovative buildings that enrich local identity and improve the performance of a built structure.

KEYWORDS: Architecture, sustainability, cultural identity, Inter-locality, interdisciplinary design, optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The problems of modern design as it pertains to the physical and social environment are interconnected.

The fast development of technology has created an antithesis, a contradiction, between the potentials of construction and their rational assimilation. This is often expressed in arbitrary conceptions with all sorts of exaggerations in the form of structures.

The architect is now facing ill-defined demands, while the means at one’s disposal are practically similar all over the world. The same materials are used to reproduce a limited array of forms. The result is that locality, i.e. the local character of a specific place is negated and destroyed. The “new” product has to be sold and is advertised in all possible ways, the aesthetic view of the public being channelled accordingly.

This can be seen in the condition of Greek architecture today. As far as it accepts and copies the globalized trends it opens a market for multinational companies (suppliers and contractors). The more it complies with these trends the more it is “approved” and advertised. However, the problems persist and become evident in the distortion of the natural environment, the chaotic and uncontrolled construction, the disdain of ancient relics, the waste of materials and energy.

An agonizing search for “new” paradigms often ends up in irrational results, while the principles of eco-design are often reduced to commercialized ideas and products of dubious quality. How can we reverse that trend? Can we minimize the damage and open prospects for the future? In my opinion, the criteria for development ought to include enhancement of the character of each individual place. The search for and reinterpretation of the identifying elements of each site would create diversity, a quality that today, more than ever before, is necessary to preserve and enhance.

In 1942, the urban planner and architect Constantinos Doxiadis coined the term 'ekistics'. It concerns the science of human settlements, and pays particular attention to ecology among other fields. [1] Architects here in Spain, have vitally participated over the years in this active dialog; the newly established Foster Foundation will certainly contribute. Here, I propose inter-locality [2] as my personal approach to synergy of sustainable design and cultural heritage.

2. PROMOTING INTER-LOCALITY

If sustainability is the process of uninterrupted productive activity based on the minimization of the negative consequences of that production (exhaustion of natural resources, pollution, etc.), its aim is the long term reproduction.

Considering that buildings (in both construction and operation) have their share in energy consumption, architecture may contribute to the minimization of the problem by producing improved designs that result in substantial energy savings.

There is an inherent continuity in any development – be it social, technical or other – that cannot be ignored. The methods used in the past to solve similar problems in different societies and localities are not to be thrown overboard.

Locality, the quality that renders a product of architecture part of its surroundings (loci) both natural and cultural, derives dynamically from the locus and includes the existing social relations at a particular time. Considering that design is improved by taking into account experience from different localities, I introduced back in 2008 the concept of Inter-locality as a synthesis of the design principles of different peoples in different localities facing similar problems. Inter-locality refers to widely accepted design principles as opposed to the concept of design globalization. Contrary to impersonal universality, it penetrates localities deriving from their qualities and creates diversity, a quality that today, more than ever before, we need to preserve and enhance. A universal concept of new localities is thus formed that may also constitute a means of symbolism of present time as a specific time-space phenomenon.

I view inter-locality as an alternative to the worldwide imposition of stereotyped forms that lead to an architecture without local character, without alternative expressions. Inter-locality's open character may lead to the appearance of new localities and/or enrich a work with universal qualities. Reference to the environment, natural or manmade, as a principle of architecture must run through design. This *genius loci* approach, perceived as both the natural and cultural environment, will make each new project distinct from any previous work.

Inter-local design as qualitative synthesis, studies how traditional architecture in different localities is connected to ecology, rational use of materials and the way of life in each epoch. It is a network of localities incorporating common principles of different civilizations, mainly deriving from local values when applied in a specific place; it maintains, enriches and reinforces the local identity.

Thus, inter-locality having an open character, may lead to the appearance of new localities or enrich a particular architectural work with universal qualities.

How do we promote inter-locality? This question brings us to the content of architectural programs for future practitioners.

3. EDUCATION AND RESEARCH

In many universities, architectural studies concentrate primarily on visual education, producing limited scholarly knowledge [3], whereas many well-esteemed organizations as EAAE advocate stronger links between theoretical and practice-based research. [4]

I believe that the faculty should be oriented towards the overall intellectual development of the students. The capacity to think is not something innate, but has to be taught. Students should be taught how to address real life contradictions in a creative way.

Theory and practice as two sides of human creative activity should not be juxtaposed. Although practice causally preceded in the past, in our era theory is determining the course of research and production in nearly every field. The theoretical conclusions confirmed in practice guide human activity.

3.1. Contemporary architecture education

I consider theoretical studies as the key to architectural education. Architectural theories are condensed collective experience, hypotheses for the “how” and “why” architecture developed the way it did. Teaching should include the history of cultural heritage and its influence on design, intellectual development and ethical issues. The study of the cultural heritage should be based on scientific principles, and avoid the sterile “return to the past” that in architecture is often expressed as copying forms of the past in today’s works. [5]

Figure 1. Up: Unités de Camping, Le Corbusier, 1956. Below: ingenious solution with local and second usage materials; built by farmers, Santorini, 2016. Both structures work superbly in terms of their congruence with the locus and clearly express their usage.

3.2. Locality expressed in contemporary terms

Cultural values are best kept alive in present works by structural diversity; by a multitude of structures that contain the identity of the natural and cultural locality and express it in contemporary terms in connection with its historical tradition. In this way an architect conveys to other people the intended meaning of the work and its relation to the cultural values.

Learning consists of the appropriation of social experience by the individual. Therefore the student mastering the history of architecture should understand the causality of phenomena and one's own role in the design and construction of buildings today.

Antiquities, for example, are characterized by locality, being inseparable with the place where they were found. But, at the same time, they contain inter-locality because of their global radiance and messages they carry to humanity. Since they derive from different historical periods, they also contain temporal Inter-locality. Moreover, inter-local is the way we treat them by obeying to widely accepted museographic principles and rules.

In designing the in situ Museum of Naxos (1994) that confirms continuous occupation for 3500 years, we attempted to recognize archetypes and develop particular forms that provide a new interpretation of the *genius loci* by expressing the identity of the historic landscape. The archaeological findings in the underground museum and their visitors were integrated into everyday life, enhancing the development of socio-cultural activities and social coherence.

The urban public space was enriched both by the exhibition of the antiquities and by the “open” management of its form. We used bricks as a modern version of an ancient material, mud-brick, which was widely used in the excavated area. This undulating solid brick wall surrounding the Museum area is extended to embrace the Museum forecourt. As an industrial material it both refers to and marks out the exhibits creating a new locality and constituting a means of symbolism of present time. [6]

Figure 2. The in situ Museum of Naxos, architect: Agnes Couvelas. Inter-locality enriches the structure with universally accepted qualities.

3.3. Ecological awareness

Architects need adopt design and construction methods in conformity with the principles of sustainability and be trained accordingly. How can they achieve this target under the conditions prevailing today? Declarations for “architecture of good intentions” are not enough neither is the formal adherence to regulations. No longer can good architecture claim to be good if it is not sustainably responsible.

The cultivation of ecological awareness presupposes a higher cultural level, an appropriate educational system leading to a new collective approach to problems, free from constrains of the market and the imposed attitude commonly known as fashion. Universities may play a decisive role in the formation of ecological awareness of the students, provided that all, teachers and students, have already adopted the principles and recognized the vital necessity of this approach.

3.4. Inventory of bioclimatic solutions

With a view to the educational means available to students of architecture and field architects, I have proposed the establishment of a novel inventory of bioclimatic solutions as applied not only to traditional settlements of the global architectural heritage but also to the individual anonymous buildings therein. The latter would provide a wealth of practical experience in condensed form from solutions applied in the structures of the past.

Figure 4. Badgir (wind tower), Jazd, Iran (photo 1995) and pigeon dove, Olympia, Greece (photo 1968) in juxtaposition.

The creation of such an inventory will require renewed research efforts in a vital field that is under gradual disappearance. Rigorous investigation will lead to a codified body of knowledge in the form of a reference guide for an evidence-based design. Moreover, blending high-tech design and ancient sustainable solutions into an integral corpus, will provide those interested in passive energy design with a reservoir of ideas and demonstrate that good design was and is sustainable design.

Figure 3. Parapets in Peloponnese (photo 1968) and at Fatehpur Sikri, India, (photo 2017) in juxtaposition.

3.5. Form optimization

Furthermore, the methods of form optimization of structures known as “topological optimization” should be included in the curriculum of architectural studies. Under a theoretical and practical approach of advanced computation the study object would be defined and understood as a parametric system of properties that determines a field of solutions or a set of alternatives. The criteria for the optimization may be energy saving, quality of living conditions or other. The application of such methods requires the cooperation of specialists from various disciplines. Seeking and welcoming advice from other specialists, as e.g. engineers or mathematicians, will not restrict design intuition; on the contrary, it will open new horizons to creative design. [7]

Figure 5. “Sails”, office building in Piraeus, Greece (photo 2014), architect: Agnes Couvelas, and private house in Kyoto, Japan (photo 1995) in juxtaposition.

4. EXAMPLES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF INTER-LOCAL PROCEDURES

I think it is preferable to present some more examples in which I have been personally involved, because I can describe everything concerning the practical and theoretical frame/background. Looking for innovative design solutions, we have implemented a number of passive bioclimatic approaches focused on the above principles, such as projects that explore the potential for using wind qualities as an expressive element in building design; projects that enhance cool air flow in the interior space, control wind and sand accumulation, protect from noise or enhance the sound

carried by the wind, deflect prevailing winds, convert the wind into a means of protection against its own force, and others.

Further to the wind treatment, we have designed adaptive building envelopes and shading systems to achieve control of natural lighting, ventilation and temperature of the inner spaces through their own transformability, surface openings and materials, including planting as a building material; in a sense, treating buildings as living organisms.

Durability, livability and energy conservation are primary requirements of our work and are incorporated through specific manipulations to environmentally friendly design, a highly topical issue at this time.

In collaboration with academic engineers with expertise in computational methods, we are currently attempting to optimize the behaviour of particular structures by modifying their shape. This is currently the topic of a study under a European Research Program. In this research, shape and performance optimization techniques are applied in order to improve the effectiveness of architectural structures in problems subject to simulation analysis and fluid mechanics. [8]

4.1. “SAILS”, shipping company building improved through performance optimization.

In this example we focus on the performance evaluation of this existing façade system to improve the occupants’ comfort. An important feature of the building envelope was the construction of a sunshade system. Its elements have been designed with such an orientation that the lighting in the interior and the view provide a natural feeling.

Optimization and effectiveness of this external shading system is further studied through simplified ray methods for modelling the light. The analysis is being conducted with energy modelling simulation programs. [9]

Figure 6. SAILS Shading devices, Office Building, Piraeus, 2014, Agnes Couvelas, Architect. West façade detail and diagrams.

4.2. Inter-local wind deflectors at the House of the Winds.

In designing this house, the locus was a constant reference point: the eroded pumice rocks, the medieval fortresses, the prehistoric settlement at Akrotiri, and the prevailing wind. The latter was exploited as a passive means of protection against its own force. Funnels embedded proximally to selected windows, force the exiting air to form an invisible “curtain” that deflects the oncoming wind, which would otherwise invade the rooms. The shape of the funnels has been determined via a combination of reflection, and a trial-and-error approach. [10, 11, 12, 13] We further study wind deflectors by applying optimization techniques in order to improve their effectiveness for future architectural structures. [14, 15]

Figure 7. The House of the Winds in Santorini, Greece, 1994, Agnes Couvelas, Architect.
East and north façade details and diagram.

4.3. Walls against sand accumulation and wind.

Such a construction has been designed for the seaside at Artemis, Greece. It concerns sand containment walls that deflect the air vertically so that the amount of sand transferred on the other side is minimal. The protection walls need to have multiple functionality; mitigate the sand-blast by deflecting the flow of the lower air layers hitting against the walls; reduce the velocity of the higher layers, while at the same time function as a temporary sand accumulator (the waves deposit and withdraw the sand).

In this project we search to optimize the wall shape by applying optimization techniques in order to improve its effectiveness in problems related to fluid mechanic [16].

Figure 8. Sand Containment Walls at Artemis, Athens, Greece, 2014, Agnes Couvelas, Architect.

5. CONCLUSION

In my opinion architectural studies should adhere to the synergy between bioclimatic design and cultural heritage through inter-locality. This requires interdisciplinary cooperation and a leading role by the Academic world.

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